

Health Worker Performance Factors in the Implementation of Infection Prevention and Control: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: Infection Prevention and Control (IPC) is a crucial component in improving the quality of care and patient safety in healthcare facilities. The success of IPC implementation is significantly influenced by the performance of healthcare workers in consistently implementing infection prevention standards and procedures. Poor adherence to IPC can increase the incidence of nosocomial infections, length of stay in hospital, mortality, and healthcare costs. This literature review aims to analyze factors influencing the performance of healthcare workers in implementing IPC. This study employed a literature review method, collecting literature through PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and Semantic Scholar using the Boolean operators AND and OR. The literature was limited to articles from 2021 to 2025 that discussed individual, psychological, and organizational factors in IPC implementation. The study results indicate that individual factors include knowledge and tenure. Psychological factors include motivation and attitude. Organizational factors include the availability of resources and facilities, supervision, compensation systems, and workload. IPC implementation is influenced by interrelated individual, psychological, and organizational factors, requiring a comprehensive approach to improving IPC compliance and patient safety.

KEYWORDS: Health worker performance, Infection prevention and control, IPC compliance, Performance factors.

INTRODUCTION

Implementing Infection Prevention and Control (IPC) is a crucial part of improving the quality of care and patient safety in hospitals. This program aims to reduce the risk of healthcare-associated infections, which can increase morbidity, mortality, length of stay, and healthcare costs (Putra et al., 2022). The success of IPC implementation is heavily influenced by the performance of healthcare workers as the primary implementers of healthcare services (Kubde et al., 2023). Healthcare worker performance reflects the ability to consistently and responsibly implement IPC standards and procedures. Poor performance of healthcare workers in implementing IPC can increase the incidence of nosocomial infections and reduce the quality of hospital services (Susanto et al., 2025).

Nosocomial infections are infections that arise while a patient is receiving treatment at a healthcare facility and are not in the incubation period upon hospital admission (Batubara et al., 2025). The most common infections include surgical site infections, catheter-associated bloodstream infections, ventilator-associated pneumonia, and urinary tract infections due to urinary catheters (Safitri et al., 2023). The incidence of these infections is significantly influenced by the behavior of healthcare workers, particularly adherence to hand hygiene, use of personal protective equipment, aseptic technique, and implementation of standard operating procedures. Failure to adhere to these practices can increase the transmission of pathogenic microorganisms between patients and from healthcare workers to patients (Batubara et al., 2025; Carolina and Melisa, 2024).

Inconsistent healthcare worker behavior in implementing IPC can increase the risk of healthcare-associated infections, which impacts patient safety and the quality of hospital services (Batubara et al., 2025; Carolina and Melisa, 2024). In addition to impacting patients, failure to implement IPC also increases the risk of occupational diseases in healthcare workers, such as hepatitis

B, hepatitis C, and HIV due to exposure to blood and body fluids (Kurnia et al., 2025). This situation can impact the institution's image and the achievement of hospital service quality indicators (Batubara et al., 2025).

Healthcare worker performance is influenced by three main factors: individual factors, psychological factors, and organizational factors (Tulasi et al., 2021). Individual, psychological, and organizational factors play a significant role in shaping healthcare workers' behavior toward implementing IPC (Kubde et al., 2023). Healthcare workers with good knowledge and skills tend to be more compliant in implementing infection control procedures (Ranoto et al., 2025). Motivation and a positive attitude are also associated with better IPC compliance. Furthermore, a supportive work environment, effective supervision, and good workload management contribute to the success of IPC implementation in hospitals (Abalkhail and Alslamah; Astari et al., 2022). Based on these descriptions, this literature review was conducted to analyze the factors influencing healthcare workers' performance toward IPC behavior in healthcare facilities.

METHODS

This study employed a literature review method aimed at analyzing factors influencing healthcare worker performance in implementing IPC in healthcare facilities. Literature was collected through the PubMed, ScienceDirect, Google Scholar, and Semantic Scholar databases using the keywords "healthcare worker performance," "infection prevention and control," "IPC compliance," "performance factors," and "healthcare worker performance," combined with the Boolean operators AND and OR to obtain relevant articles.

The literature was limited to original research articles and review articles published between 2021 and 2025, available in full text, and discussing individual, psychological, and organizational factors influencing IPC implementation by healthcare workers. Articles irrelevant to the topic, unavailable in full text, and published outside the specified year range were excluded. Literature selection was conducted through title and abstract screening, followed by full-text review to ensure alignment with the study objectives. Articles that meet the criteria are then analyzed systematically through identification of factors that influence the performance of health workers, synthesis of research results, analysis of the relationship between factors, and the preparation of a structured scientific narrative according to the focus of the literature review discussion.

RESULTS

Based on the literature search results, several articles were obtained that were relevant to healthcare worker performance factors in IPC implementation. These articles were then analyzed to identify factors that emerged in various studies. The results of the literature review are presented in the following tables.

Literature Review Based on Research Characteristics

Table 1. Literature review based on author, year, location, research design, and sample

No	First Author, Year	Study Site	Study Design	Sample (Health workers)	Sampling Technique
1	Abalkhail et al., 2021	Saudi Arabia	Cross sectional	213	Purposive Sampling
2	Fatimah et al., 2024	Indonesia	Cross sectional	53	Total Sampling
3	Kiddeer et al., 2025	Pakistan	Cross sectional	533	Convenience Sampling
4	Astari et al., 2022	Indonesia	Cross sectional	35	Total Sampling
5	Andriyanto et al., 2022	Indonesia	Cross sectional	191	Purposive and Proportional Sampling
6	Puspasari et al., 2024	Indonesia	Cross sectional	77	Total Sampling
7	Siringo-ringo et al., 2025	Indonesia	Cross sectional	34	Total Sampling
8	Mendrafora et al., 2024	Indonesia	Cross sectional	100	Purposive Sampling
9	Annisa et al., 2022	Indonesia	Cross sectional	63	Purposive Sampling
10	Kusumawati et al., 2022	Indonesia	Cross sectional	212	Cluster Random Sampling

Literature Review Based on Health Worker Performance Factors in Implementing Infection Prevention and Control
Table 2. Literature review based on health worker performance factors in the implementation of infection prevention and control

Factors	Authors (Year)	Results	<i>p-value</i>
Individual Factors			
Work tenure	Fatimah et al., 2024	Length of service is related to nosocomial infection prevention measures	0.007
	Kiddeer et al., 2025	Experience from work period influences the application of IPC standards in the work environment	<0.05
	Abalkhail et al., 2021	More than 6 years of service increases compliance with IPC	<0.001
Knowledge	Fatimah et al., 2024	Knowledge related to nosocomial infection prevention measures	<0.001
	Kiddeer et al., 2025	Good knowledge influences IPC practices in the field	<0.001
	Puspasari et al., 2024	Knowledge is positively correlated with IPC compliance	0.035
Psychological Factors			
Motivation	Astari et al., 2022	Work motivation is positively correlated with IPC compliance	<0.001
	Andriyanto et al., 2022	Motivation is statistically related to compliance with IPC implementation	<0.001
Attitude	Andriyanto et al., 2022	Attitudes are statistically related to compliance with IPC implementation	<0.001
	Siringo-ringo et al., 2025	Positive attitudes are significantly associated with high levels of health workers' compliance with hand hygiene practices	0.022
Organizational Factors			
Availability of resources and facilities	Siringo-ringo et al., 2025	Availability of facilities encourages health workers in hand hygiene	0.009
Supervision	Mendrafora et al., 2024	Nurses who receive good supervision are able to carry out IPC well	0.015
	Annisa et al., 2022	Supervision by the head of the room is significantly related to IPC compliance	0.025
Compensation System	Kusumawati et al., 2022	The compensation system significantly drives employee motivation and performance in IPC	<0.001
Workload	Puspasari et al., 2024	Workload influences nurse compliance in implementing IPC	0.002

DISCUSSION

Individual Factors in IPC Implementation

Individual factors are personal characteristics inherent in healthcare workers and contribute to their ability to perform healthcare tasks. Knowledge and tenure also play a significant role in shaping healthcare worker performance in implementing IPC.

Knowledge is a key determinant of healthcare worker compliance with IPC. Healthcare workers who understand the concept of HAIs, the principles of standard precautions, the use of personal protective equipment, and hand hygiene procedures tend to be more compliant with IPC. Good knowledge fosters awareness of infection risks and their impact on both patients and healthcare workers (Puspasari et al., 2024; Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023). Motivation and attitudes toward patient safety also play a role in shaping commitment to IPC compliance. A positive attitude toward the importance of infection prevention increases healthcare workers' likelihood of complying with applicable operational standards (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023).

Tenure also influences IPC implementation (Abalkhail et al., 2021). Longer service tenure enables healthcare workers to develop better critical and analytical thinking skills, thus healthcare workers with professional education tend to demonstrate more professional performance than healthcare workers with vocational education (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023; Noor et al., 2024). The longer a healthcare worker's service tenure, the higher their level of skill mastery and understanding of service procedures, thus positively impacting the effectiveness of IPC implementation (Wijayanti and Fitriani, 2022).

Psychological Factors in IPC Implementation

Psychological factors relate to the mental processes and individual attitudes that influence the work behavior of healthcare workers. Psychological factors include motivation, perception, and attitude toward work (Anindita, 2024). These aspects directly influence how healthcare workers respond to and carry out IPC procedures in their daily work environment (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023). Healthcare workers' perceptions and attitudes toward infection risk are the most influential psychological factors in IPC implementation (Anindita, 2024). Perception is the individual's process of interpreting work situations and environments, so a positive perception of the importance of IPC will encourage better performance. Attitudes consist of cognitive, affective, and behavioral components, with a positive work attitude directly contributing to increased healthcare worker compliance (Kidder et al., 2025). Perceived risk of infection exposure also strengthens individuals' drive to protect themselves and their patients from potential transmission (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023).

Motivation is an internal and external force that drives healthcare workers to act and maintain compliant behaviors with IPC. Motivation is closely related to fulfilling individual needs and expectations, where high work motivation will encourage healthcare workers to achieve optimal performance. Motivation and attitudes toward patient safety play a role in shaping commitment to IPC compliance. A positive attitude toward the importance of infection prevention will increase healthcare workers' tendency to comply with applicable operational standards (Astari et al., 2022; Kiddeer et al., 2025). Attitudes also influence healthcare workers' ability to adapt IPC procedures into daily work practices. Attitudes reflect relatively stable behavioral patterns and psychological characteristics, therefore, they need to be considered in human resource management to ensure that the placement and development of healthcare workers align with individual characteristics (Sulistiyorini et al., 2021; Andriyanto et al., 2022).

Organizational Factors in IPC Implementation

Organizational factors relate to the systems, policies, and working conditions created by the organization to support the implementation of healthcare workers' duties in IPC (Fortuna, 2025). Organizational factors fall into five main aspects: resources, supervision, organizational structure, compensation systems, and workload (Prihatini et al.; Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023; Kusumawati et al., 2025). These five aspects directly influence the ability of healthcare workers to consistently and optimally carry out IPC procedures. The availability of resources and facilities is a primary prerequisite for IPC implementation. The availability of facilities such as sinks, hand rubs, and personal protective equipment determines the level of healthcare worker compliance, because without adequate support, compliant behavior is difficult to consistently achieve (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023; Madamang et al., 2021). The availability of adequate resources enables healthcare workers to provide optimal healthcare services and reduces barriers to work. In addition to physical facilities, a clear organizational structure also facilitates coordination, increases accountability, and supports productive work behavior in the implementation of IPC (Lowe et al., 2021; Putra et al., 2022).

Supervision and compensation systems play a crucial role in shaping a culture of IPC compliance in healthcare facilities. Effective supervision is characterized by a leader's ability to provide clear direction, build harmonious working relationships, and create a conducive work climate, thereby improving the motivation and performance of healthcare workers (Madamang et al., 2021; Astari et al., 2022). Good supervision from above has been shown to significantly impact healthcare worker performance (Mendrafora et al., 2024). A fair and transparent compensation system also contributes to increased motivation, where intrinsic rewards such as job satisfaction and autonomy, as well as extrinsic rewards such as salary, benefits, and recognition, encourage

healthcare workers to maintain optimal performance in IPC implementation (Gaughan et al., 2021; Schiller et al., 2025). Workload is one of the most influential organizational factors affecting IPC compliance (Azak et al., 2023). High workloads can hinder the implementation of IPC procedures, even if healthcare workers have good knowledge and attitudes (Tiara et al., 2024). Dense working conditions can cause health workers to neglect certain procedures such as hand hygiene due to time pressure or fatigue (Puspasari et al., 2024).

The Relationship Between Factors on the Performance of Health Workers in the Implementation of IPC

The performance of healthcare workers in implementing Infection Prevention and Control (IPC) is influenced by the interplay of individual, psychological, and organizational factors. These three factors do not operate in isolation but interplay in shaping healthcare workers' compliance with IPC procedures in healthcare facilities (Tulasi et al., 2021). Individual factors such as knowledge, abilities, skills, education level, and length of service form the basis for understanding IPC procedures, but the implementation of compliant behavior is still influenced by psychological conditions and available organizational support (Iqbal, 2022; Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023). Psychological factors play a role in strengthening or weakening an individual's ability to implement IPC. Healthcare workers with positive perceptions of infection risk, high work motivation, and a positive attitude toward patient safety tend to be more consistent in implementing IPC procedures (Anindita, 2024; Kidder et al., 2025). Good knowledge does not necessarily result in compliant behavior without motivation and awareness of the importance of infection prevention. Conversely, motivation and positive attitudes can increase an individual's readiness to apply IPC skills optimally in the work environment (Astari et al., 2022).

Organizational factors also determine the effectiveness of individual and psychological factors in IPC implementation. The availability of facilities, supervision, organizational structure, and compensation systems are key factors in creating a work environment conducive to IPC compliance (Fortuna, 2025; Hansen et al., 2023). Healthcare workers with high knowledge and motivation can still experience obstacles in implementing IPC if facilities are inadequate or the workload is too high (Azak et al., 2023; Tiara et al., 2024). Conversely, a supportive work environment can increase motivation, strengthen compliant behavior, and help healthcare workers maintain optimal performance in IPC implementation. The interrelationship between these factors indicates that improving healthcare worker performance in IPC implementation requires a comprehensive approach. Increased knowledge and skills need to be accompanied by strengthening motivation, attitudes, and adequate organizational support so that IPC compliance behavior can be implemented consistently and sustainably. The integration of individual, psychological, and organizational factors is an important foundation for building a patient safety culture and improving the quality of healthcare services in healthcare facilities.

Implications of Performance Factors on IPC Compliance

Understanding the factors influencing healthcare worker performance in implementing IPC has important implications for healthcare facilities in improving compliance with infection prevention procedures. Individual, psychological, and organizational factors are interrelated in shaping healthcare worker behavior towards IPC implementation. Improving IPC compliance cannot be achieved through a single approach but requires integrated interventions across all three factors to ensure consistent and sustainable behavioral change (Tulasi et al., 2021; Kubde et al., 2023). From an individual perspective, healthcare facilities need to strengthen regular IPC education and training programs for all healthcare workers. Training covering the concepts of Healthcare Associated Infections (HAIs), standard precautions, hand hygiene, the use of personal protective equipment, and medical waste management can improve healthcare workers' knowledge and skills in implementing IPC procedures appropriately (Rahmawati and Dhamanti, 2021). Good knowledge and skills have been shown to be associated with higher levels of IPC compliance among healthcare workers (Puspasari et al., 2024; Ranoto et al., 2025).

From a psychological perspective, improving work motivation, risk perception, and attitudes toward patient safety need to be a crucial part of the IPC implementation program. Healthcare workers with high motivation and a positive attitude toward patient safety tend to be more consistent in implementing IPC procedures (Astari et al., 2022; Kidder et al., 2025). Establishing a positive risk perception of infection exposure is also crucial for raising healthcare workers' awareness of the impact of IPC non-compliance on both patients and themselves (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023). These efforts can be achieved through education, risk communication, and strengthening a patient safety culture in the workplace. From an organizational perspective, healthcare facilities need to ensure the availability of IPC-supporting facilities and infrastructure, such as hand rubs, sinks, and personal protective equipment, that are

easily accessible to healthcare workers. The availability of adequate facilities impacts healthcare workers' ability to consistently implement IPC procedures (Madamang et al., 2021; Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023). Furthermore, workload management and supervisory support also play a crucial role in improving IPC compliance. High workloads can cause healthcare workers to neglect certain procedures due to time pressure and fatigue (Azak et al., 2023; Tiara et al., 2024). Regular supervision, accompanied by evaluation and feedback, can improve discipline and the quality of IPC implementation in healthcare facilities (Madamang et al., 2021).

Implementing a reward system and strengthening work discipline are also crucial for improving IPC compliance. Rewarding healthcare workers who demonstrate high levels of compliance can increase motivation and maintain positive work behavior. Conversely, implementing administrative sanctions for procedural violations can serve as a form of control to improve healthcare workers' discipline in implementing IPC standards (Seilatu and Ayubi, 2023). Effective supervision, a fair compensation system, and a supportive work environment will help foster a culture of patient safety and continuously improve the quality of healthcare services (Hansen et al., 2023; Cappeli et al., 2024).

CONCLUSION

The performance of healthcare workers in implementing IPC is influenced by three main interacting factors: individual factors, including education level, knowledge, and length of service; psychological factors, including motivation and attitude; and organizational factors, including the availability of resources and facilities, supervision, compensation systems, and workload. These three factors do not operate in isolation but rather reinforce and influence each other. Improving IPC compliance requires a comprehensive approach that addresses all three dimensions simultaneously, thereby establishing a sustainable patient safety culture in healthcare facilities.

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